

Public perception of new plant breeding techniques for sustainable production of feed and food in the Czech Republic

Naděžda Čadová^{a,b}, Jaroslav Doležel^a, Ivo Frébort^{c,*}

^a Centre of Plant Structural and Functional Genomics, Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Olomouc, Czech Republic

^b Public Opinion Research Centre, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

^c Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

A survey was conducted among 1676 Czech citizens in the autumn of 2024 to explore their attitudes toward different methods of crop improvement, which are based on the modification of genetic information. The study focused on three techniques: classical mutagenesis, insertion of foreign genetic material, and genome editing. The findings revealed that a significant part of the general public was unfamiliar with these technologies and their legal status. A majority of respondents mistakenly believed that currently permitted mutation breeding using radiation or chemical mutagens is illegal, while conversely assuming that techniques strictly regulated in Europe, such as transgenesis and genome editing, are allowed. Despite using different survey methods and question wording, the study pointed to a modest positive shift in public attitudes toward new genetic technologies compared to earlier surveys. For example, support for legalising genome editing rose from 22 % in 2019 to 47.6 % in 2024, and the proportion of respondents who would buy food containing genetically modified ingredients increased from 35 % to 47.4 %. Acceptance of these methods varied across demographic groups, with younger, more educated, and male respondents showing higher levels of support. While many acknowledge potential benefits such as reduced pesticide use, concerns about safety, ethics, and environmental impact remain. In general, the Czech public demonstrates cautious optimism, underscoring the importance of transparency and clear product labelling.

1. Introduction

Genome editing offers revolutionary opportunities for plant improvement to address the challenges in feeding the growing global population [1]. To cope with the challenge, a new generation of crops adapted to climate change and suitable for sustainable, environment-friendly agriculture is needed. Developing novel crops, whether by improving existing varieties or through *de novo* domestication within a limited timeframe, will not be possible without targeted genetic modifications to achieve desired traits [2]. This can be realised either by inserting foreign genes through transgenesis, resulting in so-called genetically modified organisms (GMOs), or by using recently developed genome editing methods that allow for precise modification of a plant's genetic make-up without introducing foreign DNA. However,

the rapid development of genome editing tools such as the CRISPR-Cas system that make it possible [3] has rendered the current European regulations unsuitable, obsolete and overly restrictive, hampering the application of the new biotechnological approaches collectively called new genomic techniques (NGT) [4].

In contrast to GMO and NGT, classical mutagenesis introduced in the mid-20th century involves exposing seeds or plant tissues to radiation or chemical mutagens to induce random and to a large extent unknown genetic changes across a genome. This method has been widely used in plant breeding and is explicitly exempted from the scope of EU GMO legislation under Directive 2001/18/EC, which excludes techniques “which have conventionally been used in a number of applications and have a long safety record.” In contrast, transgenesis, where foreign genetic material with known nature and phenotypic effects is integrated,

Abbreviations: CRISPR-Cas, Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats; CRISPR, Associated protein; EU SAGE, European Sustainable Agriculture through Genome Editing; GMO, Genetically modified organism; NGT, New genomic techniques; CAWI, Computer Assisted Web Interviewing; CAPI, Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ivo.frebort@upol.cz (I. Frébort).

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falls under the GMO framework and is subject to strict EU regulations due to longstanding public concerns about unnaturalness, environmental risks, and food safety. Public acceptance of these two approaches differed, and while classical mutagenesis has remained largely ignored, genetically modified organisms have faced strong opposition in much of Europe. The 2018 ruling of the Court of Justice of the European Union (Case C-528/16) further clarified that organisms produced by NGT, such as CRISPR-Cas, are to be considered GMOs and, unlike classical mutagenesis, they are not exempt.

To support science-based policymaking in the EU, the EU SAGE network established an interactive database cataloguing genome editing applications in crops and providing comprehensive data on the use of genome editing in plant breeding [5]. These data collectively demonstrate the huge potential of new breeding approaches and underscore the importance of updating EU regulations to support innovation and competitiveness in the bioeconomy while ensuring safety and sustainability.

On July 5, 2023, the European Commission published a proposal for the regulation on plants obtained by new genomic techniques (NGT) to align existing EU legislation on genetically modified plants with new scientific developments. The scope of this initiative includes plants produced by targeted mutagenesis (techniques allowing modifications of the genome without the insertion of foreign DNA), including cisgenesis (modification using a sequence from the same or a crossable species). Introducing genetic material from non-crossable species (transgenesis) by NGT remains subject to existing legislation. This proposal, published by the European Commission, is seen as a shift towards a more science-based approach to regulating genome-edited crops and a positive step towards aligning EU regulations with global standards and fostering innovation in plant biotechnology [6]. In 2024, the new regulation passed its first vote in the European Parliament, and on 14th March 2025, the European Council approved a mandate for the trilogue negotiation phase, offering a hope to EU breeders that they will soon be allowed to include NGT in their breeding schemes [7]. It is also notable that the Panel on Genetically Modified Organisms of the European Food Safety Authority did not identify any additional hazards and risks associated with the use of NGT compared to conventional breeding techniques [8].

However, in the EU, where the strictest regulations have historically been in force, public acceptance of new technologies in agriculture and food production is among the lowest in the world [9]. For example, a survey conducted in Poland in 2019 [10] showed that Poles in general supported the research in biotechnology and genetic engineering, but opposed imported genetically modified animal feed available on the EU market. A 2019 Eurobarometer survey revealed that only 21 % of EU28 consumers had heard of gene-editing [11]. However, the level of awareness varied greatly among member states. Respondents from Finland (62 %), Estonia (57 %), and Sweden (50 %) were the most familiar with genome editing, while those from Romania (9 %), Italy (8 %), and Slovakia (8 %) were the least familiar. Public education is therefore crucial to improving acceptance and trust in these technologies across the EU.

This paper presents the results of a public opinion survey conducted in the Czech Republic within the framework of the project TowArDs Next GENeration Crops [12]. The aim of the study was to investigate public perceptions of various plant breeding techniques, including classical mutagenesis, transgenesis, and genome editing, among Czech citizens. Specifically, the study sought to explore how these perceptions vary across demographic groups, how they relate to consumer behaviour (e.g. willingness to accept or purchase genetically modified food), and how public trust in food safety and regulation influences these views. The findings are intended to inform communication strategies and evidence-based policymaking regarding the legal framework and societal acceptance of NGT.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Research methodology

The formulation of the research plan considered the assumption that a large part of the Czech public is not well informed about new breeding methods and genome modification methods, if at all. Thus, before the questions were asked, the basic facts and information related to the topic were presented to the citizens. The complete text of the questionnaire, including the accompanying texts, is included in [Suppl. Table 1](#).

The research was conducted on a sample of 1676 Czech citizens between 12 September and 1 October 2024. The questions were included in a regular survey conducted by the Public Opinion Research Centre, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences (CVVM) on the probabilistic online Our Society Panel [13]. The panel, which covers respondents aged 15 years and older, is built and maintained by the CVVM for the implementation of sociological quantitative research and public opinion research using the CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interviewing) method. Respondents who do not use the Internet are interviewed using the CAPI (Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing) method, i.e. by personal interview with a trained interviewer. This panel is constructed by probability stratified multistage sampling based on probability sampling of addresses. The methodology for constructing and maintaining the panel is comparable to that of similar foreign probabilistic online panels (e.g., Life in Australia [14], Understanding America Study [15], LISS panel [16]) and follows the rules and principles of professional ethics and practices, such as AAPOR [17], ESOMAR/WAPOR [18], and SIMAR [19]. More detailed technical information on the methodology is summarised in [Suppl. Table 2](#).

All respondents in Our Society Panel received an invitation to participate in the survey. Recruitment for this panel was conducted using a multistage stratified random sampling method based on the Czech Register of Census Districts and Buildings. Stratification considered region and municipality size, with random selection at multiple levels (municipality, building, household, individual). Respondents were eligible if they were aged 15 or older and residing in the Czech Republic. Demographic information (age, gender, education, municipality size) was collected directly through structured questions in the survey. Post-stratification weights were applied using official demographic data from the Czech Statistical Office to ensure population representativeness.

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all items. To evaluate associations between demographic characteristics and survey responses, Pearson's Chi-Square Test or Fisher's Exact Test was used, depending on the distribution and expected cell counts. The significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$. Analyses were performed using SPSS v29. No multivariate analysis was applied in the present report, as the focus was on descriptive and bivariate exploration.

2.2. Public views on the legalisation of various methods of genetic modification of crops

The first part of the research focused on assessing the Czech public's awareness of the genetic modification methods currently legally permitted for crops, both within the European Union (including the Czech Republic) and outside of it (e.g. in the United States of America). This session began with a presentation of an informational document explaining the motivation to employ genetic modification in crop improvement, the methods used and the evolution of these methods over time. Specifically, the respondents were presented with the following text, which, although necessarily brief and simplified, conveyed the essential information:

“The motivation of the first historical attempts to genetically modify crops was to speed up and streamline their improvement and develop individuals with desired traits. It was therefore about mimicking the processes that occur naturally as the genetic information of plants (and

also animals) changes over the course of evolution as the plants (and animals) adapt to the changing environment. Next, the aim was to produce crops with higher yields and resistant to various diseases and pests. Two new methods have been used to breed such crops since the mid-20th century:

1. Exposure of a plant's seeds to chemical mutagens or radiation that induces changes in their genetic information.
2. Insertion of genetic information originating from a different plant species or bacteria. Since the beginning of the 21st century, thanks to the progress in genetics and genomics, the portfolio of methods for reading and modifying hereditary information has been greatly expanded, and it is now possible to use new genomic techniques that mimic the natural processes of evolution:
3. A method of targeted modification of a specific selected genome region without inserting genetic information from unrelated species."

After receiving this information, the respondents were asked to share their opinions on whether the three crop improvement methods are, in their view, currently permitted or prohibited by law, both within the European Union countries, including the Czech Republic, and in other countries outside the European Union, such as the United States of America. Additionally, respondents were asked to express their views on whether the use of crops produced by this specific method should be legally allowed or banned in agriculture in their country.

The background information presented to the respondents was intentionally simplified to ensure clarity and accessibility for the general public, who generally lack knowledge of genetics and plant breeding techniques, in particular. While this simplification somewhat reduced scientific precision, such as the distinction between random mutagenesis and targeted genome editing, it was essential to ensure participant engagement and comprehension. Thus, genome editing was described as "mimicking natural processes" to emphasise the absence of foreign DNA transfer and the similarity of some outcomes to conventional breeding. However, we acknowledge that the likelihood of the spontaneous occurrence of some genome changes induced by editing may be very low. This limitation in phrasing, while necessary for communication, is recognised and further addressed in the Discussion.

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

The final weighted sample (Table 1) consisted of 1676 respondents

Table 1
Demographic characteristics of the survey respondents (N = 1676; weighted data).

Characteristic	Category	%
Gender	Male	47.0
	Female	53.0
Age group	15–19 years	5.4
	20–29 years	10.7
	30–39 years	15.8
	40–54 years	28.4
	55–64 years	15.8
	65 + years	23.9
Education	Primary or lower secondary	42.2
	Upper secondary	36.5
	Higher education	21.3
Municipality size	Up to 1999 inhabitants	26.8
	2000–4999	12.6
	5000–19,999	18.8
	20,000–49,999	13.6
	50,000–199,999	11.6
	200,000 and more	16.6
Region	All 14 Czech regions represented	–

aged 15 and above, with 47.0 % male and 53.0 % female participants. Age groups were distributed approximately evenly, with 23.9 % aged 65 + , and 31.9 % under 40. Educational attainment included 42.2 % with lower secondary education or below, 36.5 % with upper secondary education, and 21.3 % with higher education. The sample was geographically representative, covering all 14 Czech regions and municipalities. More detailed technical information included in [Suppl. Table 2](#).

3.2. Attitudes towards the traditional mutagenesis

The first method of genetic modification of crops investigated in our study is based on exposing the seeds, whole plants or their parts to chemical mutagens or radiation, to induce multiple random changes in genetic information (first method, hereinafter referred to as traditional mutagenesis). After reading the text with this information, respondents were asked to comment on whether the use of this method is permitted in the European Union and countries outside the European Union. The results are shown in [Fig. 1](#). The answers confirm the assumption that a significant part of the Czech public is not well acquainted with the issue of genetic modification of crops, or even not acquainted at all. This conclusion is based on a high proportion of "don't know" answers, which reached the level of two-fifths of the respondents, despite the provision of the input information. This does not differ significantly whether Czech citizens are commenting on the legislative framework within the European Union, including the Czech Republic, or the situation outside the EU.

In the context of the situation in the European Union, people were more likely to believe that the method of genetic modification of crops using chemical mutagens or radiation is prohibited, with more than two-fifths of respondents (40.5 %) expressing this opinion. The opposite opinion, that the method is allowed in the EU, was expressed by one-fifth of respondents (20.1 %). As regards the situation in countries outside the EU, people more often believed that the method is, on the contrary, allowed by law, which is the opinion of 40.4 % of Czech citizens, while about one sixth of the public (16.1 %) are convinced that it is prohibited. The data show that the majority of the Czech public is not aware of the widespread use of the crops that were prepared by classical mutagenesis in the EU (to date, over 3400 mutant varieties were officially released in more than 200 plant species worldwide [20]).

Differences in beliefs about allowing or prohibiting this method exist between men and women, people of different educational backgrounds and ages ([Suppl. Tables 3 and 4](#)). While there is no difference in the proportion of men and women who believe that the traditional mutagenesis is either legal or prohibited in the EU (20.4 % of men, 19.9 % of women), men are more likely to believe that it is not allowed (44.8 % of men, 36.5 % of women) and women are more likely to choose 'don't know' (34.8 % of men, 43.6 % of women).

If the questions concerned non-EU legislation ([Suppl. Table 5 and 6](#)), men and women were almost equally likely to believe that this method is prohibited by law (15.5 % of men, 16.7 % of women), but men were more likely to say that it is allowed (46.2 % of men, 35.2 % of women), while women were again more likely to admit that they did not know the answer to the question (38.2 % of men, 48.2 % of women). The analysis by age did not show any clear trend in the case of awareness of the authorisation or prohibition of the traditional mutation breeding in the European Union. Respondents aged between 30 and 39 are significantly more likely to be convinced that the method is permitted, while people in the youngest age group, 15–19, are significantly more likely to be convinced that the method is prohibited. The proportion of 'don't know' responses to this question increases with increasing age.

When asked if the method of chemical or radiation mutagenesis of crops under investigation is legal in countries outside the European Union ([Suppl. Table 7 and 8](#)), the trend is much clearer, with a gradually decreasing proportion of those who believe that such a procedure is legal outside the European Union (53.9 % in the 15–19 age group, 33.7 % in

Fig. 1. Awareness of permission/prohibition of the different genetic modification methods for crop breeding among 1676 respondents in the Czech Republic using the Our Society Panel [13]. The wording of the questionnaire, technical description of the survey and statistical evaluation are included in the Supplementary Material.

the 65 and older group) and a growing proportion of those who refused to comment on the question and chose the option "don't know" (30.3 % in the 15–19 age group, 54.0 % in the 65 and older group). As regards the proportion of people who are convinced that the practice is illegal in non-EU countries, it ranges between 15.1 % and 19.7 % among people aged 15–64, and is slightly lower (12.3 %) among those aged 65 + .

3.3. Attitudes towards gene insertion and targeted modification

Next we investigated public attitudes towards the genetic modification method based on the insertion of genetic information originating from a different plant species or bacteria (the second method, hereinafter referred to as gene insertion) and the method of targeted modification of particular genome region(s) without inserting foreign genetic information (the third method, hereinafter referred to as targeted mutagenesis). A comparison of the opinions of the Czech citizens on whether the use of these two methods is permitted or prohibited by law shows that, in case of the EU countries, approximately one-third of Czech citizens are convinced that it is legal to use the gene insertion and targeted mutagenesis (34.3 % and 34.4 %, respectively), while in the case of the traditional mutagenesis, based on exposure to chemical mutagens or radiation, it is significantly less - only one fifth (20.1 %). On the other hand, more than two-fifths of respondents (40.5 %) believed that the use of traditional mutagenesis is prohibited in the EU, while approximately one-fifth thought the same for the gene insertion (21.5 %) and targeted mutagenesis (19.0 %). The data show that the majority of the Czech public is either unaware or misinformed about current regulations in the EU.

3.4. Public views on allowing or prohibiting each specified method

In addition to assessing public knowledge of current regulation, the survey asked respondents for their personal opinions on whether the use of each method of plant genetic modification should be legally permitted or prohibited in agricultural practice. In this context, "allowing" refers to respondents supporting the legal acceptance and use of a given

method, while "prohibiting" reflects the view that the use should be banned by law. Respondents' views on whether the use of each method of genetic modification is allowed or prohibited in countries outside the EU are much more similar for all three methods examined. In all of them, the conviction that the use is legal exceeds the two-fifths mark (40.4 % for the traditional mutagenesis, 45.1 % for the gene insertion, 43.1 % for the targeted mutagenesis), and thus always prevails over the opposite opinion. People are most likely to be convinced of the prohibition of the use of the method outside the EU in case of traditional mutagenesis (16.1 %), while the proportions are slightly lower in case of gene insertion and targeted mutagenesis (10.6 % and 10.7 %, respectively).

The difference in the awareness of the authorisation or prohibition of the gene insertion and targeted mutagenesis of crops between men and women is mainly due to a more frequent choice of the undecided answer (don't know) of women. Uncertainty on these questions also increases with age and decreases with increasing the level of education.

The belief that crop genetic modification using chemical mutagens or radiation should be allowed in the Czech Republic and that the resulting crops should be allowed to be used in agriculture is currently held by about a quarter of Czech citizens (24 %), of whom 7 % strongly and 17 % rather agree. The opposite view, that such a practice should be banned, is held by three-fifths of the public (60 %), of whom 34 % believe this to be the case and 26 % strongly. Compared to the previous question, where people commented on the current state of legislation, there is a lower proportion of don't know responses, making up around a sixth of the sample (16 %).

Interestingly, Czech citizens are significantly more open to the possibility of legalising the use of gene insertion and targeted mutagenesis for crop breeding. The results are shown in Fig. 2. Over 44 % of Czech citizens would agree with legal permission of the method based on the insertion of foreign genetic information (9.1 % definitely agree, 35.2 % rather agree), and 33.2 % are against it (22.6 % rather disagree, 10.6 % definitely disagree). The Czech public is even more likely to agree with legal authorisation of a method of targeted modification of particular genome region(s) without inserting foreign genetic information, with 47.6 % of citizens agreeing (11.7 % definitely agree, 35.9 % rather

Fig. 2. Opinion on the permission/prohibition of different methods of genetic modification for crop breeding among respondents in the Czech Republic using the Our Society Panel [13]. The wording of the questionnaire, technical description of the survey and statistical evaluation are included in the Supplementary Material.

agree) and 26.6 % disagreeing (18.9 % rather disagree, 7.7 % definitely disagree).

4. Discussion

Public opinion research on new breeding methods and genetic modification of crops, as performed in this work, necessarily faces limitations related to the relatively low public awareness of these topics. Therefore, the presented research was initiated by briefly introducing the topic with an emphasis on the differences between individual methods of modifying plant genetic information. The accompanying text presented to respondents employed simplified phrasing that may not fully reflect the precise scientific differences, particularly between the random mutagenesis and targeted genome editing. While we recognise this limitation of our study, this approach reflected the way such technologies are usually communicated to the public. The survey was designed to measure public perception in this communication context and not to test technical comprehension. Subsequently, the research mapped to what extent people were familiar with the existing legislation, both in the European Union countries, including the Czech Republic, and outside the European Union, for example, in the United States of America. After expressing their opinion on the current state of the legislation, the respondents were always asked to express their own opinion on the matter, i.e. to indicate whether, in their opinion, the use of a given method of modifying the genetic information of crops should be permitted or prohibited by law.

Concerning the traditional mutagenesis of crops using chemical mutagens or radiation, which results in multiple random changes in their genetic information, the prevailing opinion in the Czech society is that its use is illegal in the European Union and legally permitted outside the European Union. In case of the other two methods of genetic modification of crops questioned, which consist either in the insertion of foreign genetic information, or in targeted modification of particular genome region(s) without inserting foreign genetic information, the public thinks that they are legal both in the EU and in non-EU countries, while the belief that they are allowed in non-EU countries is slightly

stronger in both cases.

Opinions on the authorisation of individual methods of crop genetic modification vary considerably in Czech society. In case of the methods based on mutation induction by radiation or chemical mutagens, disapproval is significantly more prevalent than approval. In case of the other two methods, on the other hand, consent slightly dominates and is comparable between the two methods; in case of the method based on the insertion of foreign genetic information, a higher proportion of citizens is in favour of banning it compared to the method of targeted modification of a particular genome region(s). Agreement with allowing each method largely decreases with increasing age and, except for the traditional mutagenesis, where the education did not play a significant role in respondents' views, increases with increasing education (Suppl. Table 9, 10, 11).

The Czech citizens generally believe (Suppl. Table 12) that the information about the presence of an ingredient from a genetically engineered crop should be included in the label of all products purchased (89.6 % agree, 5.6 % disagree), and a vast majority of them also believes that all foods with such an ingredient sold in the Czech Republic have a certificate stating that they are safe to eat (54.3 % agree, 38.4 % disagree). The benefit of growing genetically modified crops is then seen by a majority of the public as a reduced need for pesticides and fertilisers (66.4 % agree, 14.2 % disagree). At the same time, the majority of the Czech public does not think that any interference with the genetic information of plants is ethically unacceptable (34.5 % agree, 49.5 % disagree). However, when it comes to buying food with an ingredient from genetically modified crops, there is a slight prevalence of the opinion that one would buy such food ("I would never buy a food containing an ingredient from any genetically modified crop" – 38.4 % agree, 47.4 % disagree), as well as the opinion that eating it is not dangerous ("Eating food from any genetically modified crop is dangerous" – 39.8 % agree, 44.6 % disagree).

A comparison with earlier public opinion data reveals a modest but notable shift in Czech public attitudes toward genetic modification in agriculture. In a 2019 survey [21], 80 % of respondents had heard of genetically modified organisms (GMOs), yet only 10 % reported a clear

understanding of the term, and just 18 % expressed interest in the topic. More than half (51 %) never checked food labels for GMO content, and only 22 % considered GMO food safe, while 25 % viewed them as dangerous. In contrast, our findings from 2024 suggest a more nuanced and cautiously optimistic public stance, particularly toward new genomic techniques (NGTs). After receiving basic information about the methods, 47.6 % of respondents supported legalising targeted genome editing without foreign DNA, and 44.3 % supported gene insertion, compared to only 24 % for classical mutagenesis. Ethical concerns appear to have softened as well, with 49.5 % of respondents disagreeing that any interference with plant genetic information is inherently unethical. While 38.4 % still stated they would never buy food containing ingredients from genetically modified crops, 47.4 % expressed willingness to do so, and 44.6 % disagreed that such food is dangerous. These findings indicate that, when provided with accessible information, the Czech public is increasingly capable of distinguishing between different genetic modification methods and is more open to their use in agriculture than previously reported.

The observed increase in acceptance of genome editing and genetically modified food since 2019 may reflect growing public familiarity with these technologies, as well as broader societal shifts. It is possible that generational turnover also contributed to this trend. However, our data also show that education level and exposure to information are strong predictors of acceptance, suggesting that targeted communication and public engagement remain critical. Providing scientifically based, but clearly presented information can significantly alleviate public concerns about the unknown that new plant breeding techniques pose to them.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Our results demonstrate that after getting acquainted with basic information on the modification of the genetic information of crops and the so-called new breeding methods, at least a part of the public is able and willing to distinguish the individual methods and to express their opinion on them. In general, Czech society is slightly more favourable towards the methods under investigation and Czech citizens do not reject these methods a priori as ethically unacceptable and realise the advantages in their use. The modestly prevailing positive attitude is also reflected in the somewhat predominant willingness to purchase and consume food from genetically modified crops, as well as in the belief that such consumption does not pose a health risk.

While this study primarily explored public attitudes toward different methods of genome modification in plant breeding, it also revealed important insights into the public perception of NGT-derived products, such as food and feed. Although the respondents showed a relatively favourable view of genome editing as a technique, their attitudes toward the consumption of genetically modified products remain mixed. For example, a considerable share of the public still expressed hesitation or refusal to buy food containing ingredients from genetically modified crops. This indicates that support for the technology does not automatically imply acceptance of its applications, especially in the context of food consumption. Such perceptions have critical implications for regulatory acceptance, product labelling, and commercialisation of genome-edited products. Public concerns, particularly those related to food safety, ethics, and transparency, may influence future policy decisions, including whether certain NGT products should be exempted from labelling requirements.

Clear communication, robust safety assessments, and transparent labelling frameworks will be essential to foster trust and support informed consumer choices, thereby enabling socially acceptable and economically viable adoption of NGT-based innovations. To enhance public understanding and acceptance of genetically modified crops and products derived from them, a comprehensive and multifaceted communication strategy is essential. This should include: (1) educational initiatives, particularly those embedded in secondary and higher

education curricula, to build a solid foundation in genetic technologies; (2) targeted science communication efforts that clearly convey both the benefits and potential risks of new breeding techniques; (3) a more proactive role for trusted institutions, such as universities, public research organizations, and regulatory agencies in disseminating evidence-based information; and (4) meaningful public engagement through deliberative forums or citizen panels, enabling individuals to voice concerns, contribute to the dialogue, and help shape the governance of agricultural biotechnologies, thereby fostering trust and social legitimacy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jaroslav Doležel: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Ivo Frébort:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Naděžda Čadová:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of parts of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (Version 4) and Grammarly in order to assist with the writing style. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the article.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nbt.2025.08.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2025.08.002).

Data availability

Underlying data for this article is available at the Czech Social Science Data Archive with the identifier <https://doi.org/10.14473/CSDA/OT34HB>.

[Česká veřejnost o nových technikách šlechtění](https://doi.org/10.14473/CSDA/OT34HB) (Czech Social Science Data Archive)

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